

SOME ROMANIAN PERSPECTIVES ON EDUCATION AND TRAINING FOR THE DIGITAL ERA AND SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVENESS

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The European Parliament Resolution of February 16, 2023, on the European Union's strategy to promote industrial competitiveness, trade, and quality jobs (2023/2513 (RSP)) proposes 'the digital transformation of the economy and society as a digital sovereignty in an open manner, based on *strong support for science, research, development, and the scientific community.*'

This also implies a focus on education systems and the need for a "compass," following the model of the *Compass for the Digital Dimension 2030: the European model for the digital decade* (as outlined in the European Commission's Communication on the 9th of March, 2021), based, among other things, on "*skills (ICT specialists, basic digital skills), digital transformation of enterprises, secure and sustainable digital infrastructures, digitization of public services.*"

With such an objective and mechanisms in place, ensuring the security of education systems' inclusion is certain.

To achieve this goal and to advance the field of education, emphasis is placed on members of the educational community, especially teachers, who should be "adequately trained, qualified, and equipped to effectively use technology in their teaching methods."

EU Decision 2022/2481 of the European Parliament and of the Council (2022, p. 14) highlights "teaching digital technologies to better prepare students for short- and long-term entry into the labor market."

The European Union's proposals aimed at ensuring the digital transformation of education systems, targeting a digital goal by 2030, include "*sustainable digital infrastructure* for connectivity and *integration* of the DESI (Digital Economy and Society Index) into the report on the status of the digital decade to monitor progress towards digital targets" (*ibid*).

For the Romanian pre-university education sector, the two proposals from the EU signify a reconsideration of the principles of system development,

a reset towards *sustainable competitiveness*, understood in accordance with the European Agenda for Competences for Sustainable Competitiveness, Social Equity, and Resilience, which includes "professional skills and education, as well as *ecological and digital transitions*, ensuring inclusion" (EU Decision 2022/2481, p. 16).

The European Agenda for Competences for Sustainable Competitiveness (Epale, 2020: 17,

https://epale.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/communication_30june_v2.pdf)

promotes competences, stating that they are "essential for sustainable competitiveness, resilience, and ensuring social equity because they provide the skills needed to master ecological and digital transitions."

They are a "response to the need for companies to remain competitive while ensuring social equity for all" (*ibid*).

The Coronavirus crisis has highlighted the importance of possessing the right skills for strategic sectors to perform and for individuals to cope with life and career transitions.

In particular, it has emphasized the need for *digital skills* in many aspects of people's daily lives and for business continuity.

Remote work and distance learning have become a reality for millions of people in the European Union.

Having the right skills means being able to stay easily employed and to master transitions in the workplace.

This requires ensuring *equal access to additional skills development opportunities*.

This entails *strengthening existing skills and access to "real-time" information, a new approach to education and training*, modern, attractive, and flexible for the digital era and ecological transition.

Stimulating lifelong learning can be achieved through *individual learning accounts*, which allow "participation in training activities relevant to the labor market and facilitate access to employment" (Council Recommendation, 2022, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/ro/press/press-releases/2022/06/16/council-recommendation-on-individual-learning-accounts-to-boost-training-of-working-age-adults/>).

Through this agenda, the Commission establishes a new and dynamic approach to skills policy at the European Union level, aiming to guide member states and *help drive the ecological and digital transition* and ensure recovery from the socio-economic impact of the coronavirus pandemic.

The relationship between *sustainable competitiveness of education systems and digital transition* is based on the concept of new skills and abilities that education systems must focus on.

It is vital to understand what skills education systems should pursue, and therefore, anticipating and identifying new and in-depth information about competencies represents the key to such developmental directions.

Alongside *new competencies*, the relationship between *the sustainable competitiveness of education systems and digital transition* is supported by *digital technology*, a context that facilitates personalized learning, its flexibility, and person-centeredness.

The role of digital technology in supporting sustainable competitiveness through the reconsideration of digital education from this perspective is defined by the *Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027)* (2020, p. 3):

- "ensuring inclusive and high-quality digital education through relevant educational content,
- transforming education for the digital era,
- adequate investments in connectivity, equipment, organizational capacity, and skills,
- the key role of digital education in increasing equality and inclusion,
- obtaining essential digital skills for all educators,
- achieving digital literacy,
- acquiring basic digital skills by any citizen,
- encouraging advanced digital skills,
- achieving inclusion."

Achieving the outcomes of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), according to UNESCO (2017, p. 48), is accomplished through "cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioral learning," aiming at cross-cutting key competencies for ESD achievement.

The 2030 Agenda, adopted by the UN General Assembly (2015, p. 6), is "a global framework for redirecting humanity towards a sustainable path" and presents 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with a "transformative and inclusive" role for the "major challenges of humanity's development."

These are: "No Poverty, Zero Hunger, Good Health and Well-being, Quality Education, Gender Equality, Clean Water and Sanitation, Affordable and Clean Energy, Decent Work and Economic Growth, Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure, Reduced Inequalities, Sustainable Cities and Communities, Responsible Consumption and Production, Climate Action, Life Below Water, Life on Land, Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions, Partnerships for the Goals" (*ibid*).

It's a comprehensive approach "to ensure a sustainable, peaceful, prosperous, and equitable life on Earth for everyone, both now and in the future" (UN, 2015, p. 7).

There are "social needs for the fields of education, health, social protection, climate change, and environmental protection.

The overcoming of "key systemic barriers to sustainable development" is pursued (*ibid*).

Referring to the field of education, Irina Bokova, Director-General of UNESCO, asserts on this occasion that "education can and must contribute to a new vision of sustainable global development" (UN, 2015, p. 4).

The approach to Education for Sustainable Development aims to "empower informed decision-making and responsible action for the integrity of the environment, economic viability, and a just society for present and future generations" (*ibid*).

UNESCO (2017, p. 7) presents the purpose of Education for Sustainable Development as "developing skills that help individuals reflect on their own actions, considering their current and future impacts, social, cultural, economic, and environmental."

ESD is understood as (UNESCO, 2017, p. 7) "an integral part of the quality of education, inherent in the concept of lifelong learning, holistic and transformative education through the content and outcomes of learning, pedagogy, and learning environment."

In this regard, the transformation of education requires "a shift from teaching to learning, an action-oriented, transformative pedagogy that supports self-directed learning, participation and collaboration, problem orientation, inter- and transdisciplinarity, and the connection between formal and informal learning, the development of key competencies necessary for promoting sustainable development" (*ibid*).

Such an approach ensures the sustainable transformation of the education sector as a whole, to the extent that educators, in a unified and systemic manner, demonstrate motivations and attitudes based on professional training and preparation to implement teaching approaches oriented towards ESD and the sustainability of the field.

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is a recognized part of Target 4.7 of the Sustainable Development Goals and identifies, according to UNESCO (2017, p. 8), "learning objectives, suggests themes and learning activities for each Sustainable Development Goal (SDG), describes implementation at various levels, from course design to national strategies."

In this sense, the UNESCO document (2017, p. 10), based on the Agenda set by the UN, presents the *competencies for Education for Sustainable*

Development as "specific attributes needed by individuals to act sustainably and the cognitive, affective, volitional, and motivational elements, interactions between knowledge, abilities and skills, motives, and specific affective dispositions."

The transversality, multifunctionality, and context independence of these competences provide the superior level of competences for Education for Sustainable Development in the form of key competences with a "broader scope," *called transversal competences for advanced sustainable development*.

Authors like de Haan, 2010; Rieckmann, 2012, (in UNESCO, 2017, p. 10) detail *key/transversal competences for sustainability*: "systematic thinking competence, normative competence, strategic competence, collaboration competence, critical thinking competence, self-awareness competence, integrated problem-solving competence".

These *transversal competences for sustainability* are related to the 17 Sustainable Development Goals and generate specific learning objectives that "help students transition to a sustainable world" (*ibidem*).

The specific learning objectives for each of the SDGs describe their achievement in the cognitive domain as "the knowledge and skills needed to better understand the SDGs," in the socio-emotional domain, which "includes social skills that enable collaboration, negotiation, and communication, as well as self-reflection to promote the SDGs," and in the behavioral domain, oriented towards action (*ibidem*).

The implementation of learning for SDGs through Education for Sustainable Development is recommended by the UN (2016, p. 7) and monitored through the global indicator for Target 4.7, "the extent to which (i) global citizenship education and (ii) education for sustainable development are integrated at all levels in: (a) national education policies, (b) curricula, (c) teacher education, and (d) student assessment".

For Romania, from the perspective of sustainable competitiveness, according to the *Strategy for Romania's Sustainable Development 2030* (2020, p. 37), education will be "of quality and will promote lifelong learning opportunities for all".

The proposed mechanisms are "access to and participation in quality education."

Access refers to all children's access to early education, while participation refers to "equitable and quality primary and secondary education, leading to relevant and efficient outcomes."

In this context, "all students acquire the knowledge and skills necessary to promote sustainable development" (*ibidem*).

The domains included in *Romania's Sustainable Development Strategy 2030* are "formal education, educational infrastructure, early school leaving rate, and dropout rate, lifelong learning, education for sustainable development, financing, adopted reforms" (2020, pp. 37-39).

As 2030 Targets, *The Strategy* (2020, p. 40) proposes "the acquisition by students of the knowledge and skills necessary to promote sustainable development, including through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, appreciation of cultural diversity, and the contribution of culture to sustainable development."

It is proposed to "expand sustainable development as principles and specialization in higher formal education and emphasize the role of interdisciplinary research in the development of a sustainable society."

The document represents the national legislation transposition of the United Nations' *2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development* (2015).

By 2030, the achievement of aspects related to (2015, p. 34) "access to free, equitable, and quality education, relevant skills for workforce participation, knowledge and skills necessary to promote sustainable development through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and non-violence, global citizenship, appreciation of cultural diversity, contribution of culture to sustainable development, substantial increase in the supply of qualified teachers through international cooperation for teacher training in developing countries" is foreseen.

Among the scaffolding objectives of this Agenda, the one referring to *Strengthening the means of implementation and revitalizing the global partnership for sustainable development* includes important areas for sustainable competitiveness: finance, technology, trade, and capacity building.

These are elements that, in European Union documents, are rethought in terms of concepts such as sustainable competitiveness, social equity, and resilience.

We are witnessing an evolution of the concepts used by international organizations (United Nations, European Union), focusing on the individual and community, on rights and progress, on common values.

The field of education must be transformed based on sustainability principles, precisely because of the contribution education systems make to social and economic balance. One mechanism for this is the digitization of education, encompassing aspects related to digital technology and the training of teachers for the digital era.

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